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The Influence of Social Media on the Culture of Saying Islamic Greetings in Mtsn 1 Banda Aceh Students

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Abstract

Nowadays, technology has become a daily necessity. With the development of time and technology, new terms of greeting have begun to emerge. However, what is feared is the fading of the existence of the culture of greeting in Islam, namely, Assalamu'alaikum. This concern is caused by other greetings that tend to be considered more contemporary. Meanwhile, greetings are also included in the identity of an Islamic believer. This study aims to determine the effect of social media development on the culture of greetings in Islam and was conducted at MTsN 1 Model Banda Aceh with a sample of 20 students in class VIII-1. The method used is qualitative, through questionnaire interviews in the form of a Google Form. The results showed the highest percentage of 96% that students in class VIII-1 tended to answer greetings more often from their friends who greeted them, namely Assalamu'alaikum, which can be concluded that self-awareness and initiative owned by them to say greetings were still quite lacking. Meanwhile, the lowest percentage of 72% shows that there are still many content creators who have not implemented greetings in their content.

Keyword: Social media; Islamic; Greetings; Students; Aceh

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INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, where technology is increasingly advanced, it is undeniable that the presence of the internet is increasingly needed in everyday life, both in socialization, education, business, and so on (Putri, Nurwati, & Santoso, 2016; Zainuddin, T., & Ramdan, 2019; Munidar, 2024). We live in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, where there are many extraordinary developments in technology. At this time, technology has become a daily necessity. Plus, the COVID-19 pandemic, which requires all activities to be carried out from home via the internet, This certainly causes dependence on technology, for example, cellphones. Cellphones were originally only owned by people in need, but as time goes by, cellphones are now even owned by all groups, both those who really need them and those who don't really need them (Kogoya, 2015; Bahri, K., & Furqany, 2019; Cristina, 2024). However, the times are growing and continuing to develop, so cellphones have now become a necessity for many people, especially students. With the presence of cellphones, students can more easily communicate and complete group assignments. However, of course, cellphones have a negative impact if misused (Wijaya, T. S. I., & Sahlan, 2021).

In general, cellphones are also used to use social media. Social media is an online medium where users can more easily communicate, participate, share, and create content, including blogs, social networks, wikis, forums, and virtual worlds (Cahyono). Social media, especially Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and Facebook, generally give rise to new terms of address. Thus, many are more interested in using the term rather than saying greetings in Islam. However, there are also many who start their messages with greetings. Although greetings are generally used for formal messages, such as between students and teachers (Saputra, R., & Irma, 2019; Zurika, E., & Daud, 2020; Johan, 2024), This shows that salam is one of the ethics that should be familiarized with, not only to greet the teacher but also to friends. Social media really has a big influence on the lives of its users, especially since it is generally used by teenagers (Ibrahi, 2024).

Social media such as TikTok, which provides videos lasting 15 seconds to 3 minutes, is usually used as a place to have fun. Not only having fun, many content creators on TikTok convey aspirations, preaching, and social experiments. However, there are still many content creators other than preachers who start their videos with greetings. In fact, it would be very useful if they started their videos with greetings so that the audience was influenced and motivated to get used to saying greetings (Wu et al., 2022; Barta et al., 2021; Ren et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2023).

This research was inspired by previous research from Riswandi Raja in 2019, with the title "The Application of Greetings as an Ethic of Politeness in the Perspective of Da'wah in Batukaropa Village, Bulukumba Regency." In which he examined the application of greetings as an ethic of politeness from the perspective of da'wah. Therefore, researchers innovate new research by examining the influence of social media on the pronunciation of greetings.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this research is to find out the influence of social media development on the culture of saying greetings.

Research Benefits

Theoretically:

1. Knowing the influence of social media development on the ethics of saying greetings.
2. Reference material for the influence of social media development on the ethics of greeting.

Practically:

1. As a reminder for Muslims to get used to saying greetings.
2. To motivate people to always say greetings.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach. The use of a qualitative approach in this study is in accordance with the research problem to be studied, namely the influence of social media developments on the culture of saying greetings.

Location and Research Subjects

The research was conducted at MTsN 1 Model Banda Aceh, which is a favorite madrasah in Banda Aceh City and is a National Research Excellence Madrasah. The research subject is a source of data that provides clarity on the issues studied. In this study, the subjects were 20 students in VIII-1 Research.

Data Collection Technique

The research approach used in this research is qualitative, so the data collection techniques used include:

1. Observation

Observation is a data collection technique that has specific characteristics when compared to other techniques. Observation is done by collecting data by observing ongoing activities (Sugiyono, 2015). From this understanding, in this study, the researchers used direct observation and participation. This observation was carried out at MTsN 1 Model Banda Aceh by observing the behavior of students when meeting with friends, teachers, and families, such as parents who pick up their children.

2. Interview

Interviews are a data collection technique conducted through question and answer. In this study, interviews were conducted with 20 students of class VIII-1 through a questionnaire in the form of a Google Form distributed in the class group.

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis technique is a technique that discusses the process of processing data and information that has been obtained during research to get the results of the research. In this study, researchers processed data derived from interviews through a questionnaire in the form of a Google Form using the interview data analysis technique. To calculate the percentage, the formula is:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

Description:

P: Percentage

F: Number of values obtained

N: Maximum number of scores

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

This research was conducted through a Google Form distributed to 20 students in class VIII-1 as representatives. Researchers have presented 10 statements, namely, 7 positive statements and 3 negative statements. The score of each answer is 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. In a positive statement, if the sample answers strongly agree, it will get a score of 5, an agree statement will get a score of 4, a sometimes statement will get a score of 3, a disagree statement will get a score of 2, and a strongly disagree statement will get a score of 1. On the other hand, in a negative statement, if the sample answers strongly agree, it will get a score of 1, an agree statement will get a score of 2, a sometimes statement will get a score of 3, a disagree statement will get a score of 4, and a strongly disagree statement will get a score of 5. The percentage data of the research results is presented in the table below.

Table 1. Percentage Data of Research Results

No	Statement	Percentage Result
1	I greet friends/teachers/family when I meet them.	81%
2	I say greetings when sending messages to friends/teachers/family.	88%
3	I greet my friends/teachers/family when they call or receive a call.	92%
4	I often come across content that starts with a greeting.	72%
5	I didn't realize when someone greeted me, because I was engrossed in social media.	76%
6	I say greetings when entering a room (except the toilet).	82%
7	I often start a chat with P, Hello, Hi etc. rather than greetings.	63%
8	When my friends send me a message that begins with a greeting, I always answer their greeting.	96%
9	I feel that the development of social media has led to new terms of address, which has led to a decrease in greetings.	89%
10	I feel shy to say greetings.	90%

Based on table 4.1 above, we can see that with a percentage of 81%, as many as 20 students in class VIII-1 say greetings when meeting friends, teachers, or family. They also say greetings when sending messages to friends, teachers, or family, with a percentage of 88%, and they also say greetings when calling or receiving a phone call, with a percentage of 92%. This shows that the percentage of greetings when calling or receiving a phone call is higher than when sending a message.

Then, students in class VIII-1 also often encounter content that begins with greetings with a percentage of 72%. With a percentage of 76%, they did not realize when someone greeted them because they were busy playing social media. They also say greetings when entering a room other than a toilet, with a percentage of 82%, and with a percentage of 63%, they more often start a chat with P, Hello, Hi, and so on than saying greetings.

When their friends send them a message that begins with a greeting, they always answer their friend's greeting with a percentage of 96%. Also, with a percentage of 89%, they feel that the development of social media that creates new terms for greetings causes a reduction in the pronunciation of greetings. And in the last statement, with a percentage of 90%, they disagreed with being ashamed to say greetings.

Discussion

After the research was conducted, the highest percentage of statements was located at number 8 with the statement, "When my friends send me messages that begin with greetings, I always answer their greetings," with a percentage of 96%. This shows that students in class VIII-1 tend to answer greetings more often from their friends who greet them, indicating that their self-awareness and initiative to say greetings are still quite lacking. This is in line with the results of Raja's research in 2016, which explains that the inhibiting factors for greeting include the living environment, modern life, and technological factors.

The lowest percentage is in number 4 with the statement, "I often find content that begins with greetings," which has a percentage of 72%. This shows that many content creators have not implemented greetings in their content. In fact, one of the noble deeds that must be done by a Muslim towards other Muslims is to spread or say greetings, both to people who know and not (Hidayatulloh, 2011).

The culture of greeting should be preserved because it is very important for future generations. However, one of the reasons that the culture of greetings is starting to be rare is because people do not know the meaning of the greeting. This is in line with Raja (2016), who explains that some people do not know or understand the meaning contained in greetings. Whereas if someone knows the meaning contained in greetings, it is easier to apply it. Because greetings are da'wah that contain politeness values that are conditional on meaning. Supported by Shodiqin (2011), who, in the results of his research, stated that saying or answering greetings is part of the practice of worship that can be valuable on the side of Allah SWT. Saying greetings (Assalamu'alaikum) cannot be equated with saying good morning, good afternoon, or other congratulations because it contains a very beautiful meaning.

In statement number 9, with a percentage of 89%, they agree that the development of social media that creates new terms causes the culture of greeting to be underestimated. However, they say hello when they meet friends, teachers, or family, with a percentage of 81%. This shows that the environment is very influential in character building, which is in line with Ahsanulkhaq's (2019) finding that the supporting factors in the formation of students' religious character through the habituation method include the full support of students' parents and the joint commitment of school residents to realizing a religious culture in schools, facilities, or infrastructure that support the implementation of religious activities.

The development of social media led to the emergence of new terms that resulted in the pronunciation of greetings decreasing, even though it would be very beneficial to greet others. With a qualitative research method, it can be concluded that the development of social media is quite influential on the culture of greeting. This greeting culture can be familiarized from an early age and from the surrounding environment, especially the school environment for students. It is hoped that with this research, it can foster a sense of self-awareness to get used to saying greetings.

CONCLUSION

The development of social media led to the emergence of new terms that resulted in the pronunciation of greetings decreasing, even though it would be very beneficial to greet others. With a qualitative research method, it can be concluded that the development of social media is quite influential on the culture of greeting. This greeting culture can be familiarized from an early age and from the surrounding environment, especially the school environment for

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